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SIMON: an ICT proposal for the mobility impaired citizens

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Abstract

SIMON is a demonstration project with four large scale pilots in Madrid, Lisbon, Parma and Reading aiming to use ICT services to promote the independent living and societal participation of mobility impaired people in the context of on-street public parking areas and multiple transport modes.

The activities to adapt the existing ICT infrastructures in the pilot sites are summarized in this document. The SIMON services are instantiated to provide the functionalities required by each of the cities, and while there are some of them that are common for all the pilot sites, some others are particular and have required specific integrations that are detailed in this document.

Keywords:

Disabled citizen, ICT mobility services, pilot sites

The need, the context

In 1998, a recommendation on a parking card for people with disabilities¹ was presented to provide for the standardisation of the layout of parking cards for people with disabilities and their recognition by the EU countries, in order to facilitate such people's freedom of movement by car. This **EU standardised model of parking card for the disabled** (commonly known as Blue Badge) allows a disabled person who is entitled to use certain parking facilities in his EU country of residence to move more easily in the territory of another EU country and avail themselves of all the parking facilities granted to the card-holders in that EU country.

More than 25 years later, this parking card is widely used in all EU member states, which regulate on the rights and define the procedures for granting the card. Nevertheless, the misuse of the European parking card for disabled people has become a reality and a headache for public authorities in charge of managing the permissions and the use of the public space for parking purposes. Furthermore,

¹ Council recommendation of 4 June 1998 on a parking card for people with disabilities (98/376/EC)

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accessibility issues concern persons with disabilities and older population, and technology is required to promote successful actions that enable them to live more equally alongside those people without disabilities.

People with reduced mobility is often described as a single homogeneous group, however it is a heterogeneous group of people that differ in age and life styles, physical and mental characteristics, or travel patterns and transport needs.

Thus, even if the accessibility barrier may be the same, the response to overcome such barrier should attend the specific needs of each end-user. There is a need to first identify the requirements of each targeted type of citizen with reduced mobility in order to improve their mobility capabilities.

The use of new technologies can provide innovative tools aiming at offering appropriate information services to users with unconventional needs. Most of the times, difficulties in collecting enough information (in terms of quantity and quality) about urban accessibility to provide effective routing/mapping services is decisive in order to offer a service which satisfies the user expectations.

State of the art

Many weaknesses and gaps to be filled have been detected after a deep review on the state-of-the-art apps for mobility impaired users.

First, there is usually a lack of integration between different modes of transport. Some of the most commonly used applications, (*TripGo*, *Google Maps* or *Transit App*) allow the selection of the preferred mode (public transport, private car, walking), not with real multimodality. Furthermore they do not consider accessibility or the needs of mobility impaired users. Another important need is the location of specific accessibility landmarks (parking spots, accessible services, transport, etc.). Some apps offer these functionalities: *Accessibility Plus*, *It's Accessible*, *Mob Ramp*, *WheelMate*, *Wheelmap*, *On Wheels*, etc (all of them available at Google Play Store). Although these are interesting initiatives, they do not integrate the big data of public authorities, using only private material that can become easily out of date or information provided by the users themselves, acting like social networks in accessibility. This can work, always that the reliability and validity of the information is contrasted or updated and the continuous participation of a big number of users is granted. Finally, there are different apps that have been created to help disabled users to find reserved parking spaces (*Disabled Park*, *Parkible*, *Park-abled* and many others). They rely on the identification of the spots by the users and they are usually only focusing a unique city; new solutions are currently being developed based on the sensor-based monitoring of reserved parking lots (1), which substantially improves the detection of a correct use of the reserved parking places for the disabled

As a conclusion, none of the solutions combine the different functionalities required to ensure an integrated and complete mobility in a unique application: multimodal navigation (including data on accessibility and accessible transport through the big-data of cities), location and navigation to reserved parking spaces, access to restricted areas, adapted interface, etc. Especially, there is no application that can integrate these aspects with the use of a parking card for people with disabilities to validate parking and prevent fraud.

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The development of the SIMON solution requires the smart connection of some existing services and the creation of others that will manage the information gathered by the existing ones, using the current infrastructure of the cities; however, the connection and interaction among services has to be transparent for the users to ensure the mobility experience is well accepted and valuable for them. The capabilities of potential end users, from physical, cognitive and emotional point of view, are taken into account for designing the system. The extensive work done in SIMON to characterize users' needs in relation with functionality, accessibility, usability and aesthetic of the services and applications facilitates now the understanding of a product aimed at people with special needs. The users of the platform are:

- **Individuals** that plan their trips using seamlessly public and private transport modes. A multimodal navigation offer is used and real-time information about public transport and parking areas can be obtained. The common European Disable Badge is enhanced by contactless technologies in order to allow the disabled citizen to make use of specific parking lots and to access to restricted urban areas.
- **Public authorities** that can manage the use of the public space for parking purposes, and can get information on the use of the public parking areas, reducing in this way the fraud while enabling the establishment of policies promoting the sustainable use of all modes of transports. One important job in the management of a parking service is its outdoor control. The operator has the duty to offer a good parking service, and within its main tasks, fraud has to be avoided in every way: users that do not pay the parking right, who exceed time limits, occupy reserved parking spaces for disabled people without having the right, and so on.

The SIMON Platform

The Public Authority Tool

The tool for the local authorities consists on the following two modules: first, **the Backoffice Services** running in background, without a user interface, which are installed in the SIMON servers and generate log files for audit and diagnosis of failures. Second, the **SIMON Authority Operator Website** that provides the user interface for the authority operation interaction with SIMON system. As a web application, it is deployed in the Internet Information Server (IIS) and the users can get access to it by means of a Web browser.

The mobile application for controllers

SIMON CONTROLS is the mobile application used by the authorized controller to check the validity of parking rights of disabled badge holders. This enforcement application is used to verify that a user has been correctly validated in the system for occupying or leaving a parking space. In case of not validation or fraud, the controller is able to notify and impose a penalty to the user through the application. The SIMON CONTROLS app is univocally linked to the Backoffice tool, since it is used by the local authorities. Infractions can be reported and registered in the server. The information can be later used by the municipalities to act according their law and restrictions. As an additional function, the controller can notify the real status (busy or free) of a reserved parking space.

Figure 1 – SIMON CONTROLS app

The mobile application for citizens

The **SIMON Mobile app** provides the mobile frontend enabling mobility impaired users to leverage the capabilities of the SIMON services. In particular, it enable holders of disability badges to use their special rights (e.g. parking at spots reserved for disabled persons, access to traffic restricted areas of the city) in the city that issued the card.

Figure 2 – SIMON Mobile app

In addition, the application enables multi-modal navigation including real-time information (where available). To do this, the SIMON mobile application and the associated backend services integrate with data sources provided by the city administration or public transit operators. Towards this end, SIMON rely on the developed implementations of data adapters that convert the available data from different formats into the standardized and interoperable data formats leveraged by the mobile application and services.

Adapting the existing ICT infrastructure

SIMON has implemented and presented an open platform that integrates a set of ICT services available in the different test sites. These services aim at enhancing the experience of mobility impaired people by providing technology-based solutions. This system requires the smart connection of some existing services and the creation of others, in a way that this connection and interaction among services is transparent for the users and provides a valuable tool for them. The pilot cities where SIMON services are deployed are Madrid (Spain), Lisbon (Portugal) and Parma (Italy), and in

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the last weeks Reading (UK) has also joined the project so the adaptation of the SIMON services is still ongoing.

An overview of the SIMON approach, reference architecture and services is described in (2). The ICT services and applications have been implemented and tested in a small scale pilot, whose results were assessed from a double perspective: functionality and usability. This process has been detailed in (3). The last stage in the SIMON Preparation Phase finishes with the deployment and adaptation of these ICT services at each of the pilot cities. Thus, the services are instantiated to provide the functionalities required by each of the cities and while there are some of them that are common for all the pilot sites, some others are particular and have required specific integrations that are detailed in this paper.

Madrid pilot site

Madrid has set up a smart on-street parking system, which incorporates the most modern ICTs and is intended to be an instrument to regulate the traffic and contribute to the city's air quality policy. This platform is based in the Regulated Parking System (in Spanish, SER) which has been improved and made reality recently, after a bidding procedure which finished with the definitive entry into force of the Madrid Integral Mobility Platform by July 2014.

This platform not only includes the SER but also a system to control the urban areas restricted to residents: the Residential Priority Areas (APR) are spaces where vehicular access to non-residents is restricted in order to preserve the sustainable use of roads inside them, as well as lower levels of noise and air pollution such spaces. Access control to the APR is done with cameras that are located in their access roads, by capturing an image of the rear license plate of the vehicle. The number of captured license plate is contrasted with the database, starting disciplinary proceedings to vehicle owners whose access is not authorized.

The new smart SER, which includes smart park meters to regulate and control the on-street parking operations, the APR control access based on plate recognition, and a very advanced open data ecosystem, as the Madrid Transport Authority's Dataset (4) are the existing infrastructure to be adapted to in order to integrate the new SIMON ICT services for the Madrid pilot site.

First, smart parkmeters count with a system information service that provides an estimation of the occupancy of the on-street parking based upon the tickets sold by the park meters and other electronic means (mobile application) in the recent period. In order to use this functionality to obtain some information about parking places availability, an adaptor has been developed in order to convert this occupancy estimation into an estimated number of park spaces, and to normalise the data and make it consistent with SIMON data model.

Secondly, the restricted areas –APRs– control system provides a service to Madrid citizens that allows them to register the plate number of their vehicle and also to notify when they are using a car plate different from that which has been previously registered in the system. In principle, all those citizens who hold an EU disabled badge have the right to move around Madrid APRs, but they have to previously register in the system. SIMON integrates this service in its functionality, both reducing the

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fraudulent misuse of the system and facilitating the dynamic registration of number plates for short time periods when disabled citizens travel on a vehicle that is not the one they usually make use of. This ensures that they shall not be charged or fined for entering these areas. Thus, an adaptor has been developed in order to translate the access request made through SIMON app into the data model and data formats used by the Madrid access control system. The integration provides additional control for validating the access to the area, performing checks like ensuring that the user is near or inside the restricted area by the time of requesting the validation.

Lisbon pilot site

Lisbon has been working in recent years to improve the mobility platform, as part of their Smart City strategy. Most of the efforts are addressing the management of parking places but also the enhancement of the mobility for the impaired citizens. Thus, the new mobility platform encompasses not only a set of new services and applications aimed to make easier the daily experience of the Lisbon citizen, but also includes a number of programmes as "Lisboa 100% acessível" to promote different actions and activities for the disabled.

Lisbon pilot does not require the integration of any specific hardware component. EMEL, the parking operator in Lisbon, is integrating the SIMON CONTROLS on the app already used by the EMEL Enforcement Officers in Lisbon.

Parma pilot site

Parma started as a pilot city in the project with a system already in use to manage the access to Areas of Limited Transit (ZTLs). The creation and management of these ZTLs has the objective to induce citizens in the proper use of urban space, preserving sensitive areas from excessive traffic and making the city less chaotic, less polluted and more liveable. One of the most innovative elements in this platform is the permit already including a RFID tag to identify the users.

In the Licence Plate Recognition system there are six access control points to the traffic limited zone and at each control point there is a camera that photographs each vehicle transiting through the access point.

The Parma pilot has required the integration of the pre-existing control system for the restricted areas. This service is provided to Parma disabled citizens for registering the number plate of their vehicle, what ensures that they shall not be charged or fined for entering the areas. SIMON integrates this service in its functionality, both reducing the fraudulent misuse of the system and facilitating the dynamic registration of number plates for short time periods when disabled citizens travel on a vehicle that is not the one they usually make use of.

Conclusions

The present paper details all the elements involved in the adaptation and integration of SIMON system and explains how the different services have been implemented in the three test sites. Due to the differences among them, three different implementation descriptions are presented. Despite of that, a

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great effort has been made to present all the services in all the test sites in an integrated manner, aiming at achieving an overall mobility system, with the intention to act as first step implementation process towards a Europe-wide Mobility for Impaired Users framework.

After the adaptation process, the system is ready for proceeding with the execution of tests within the large scale phase of the project.

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References

1. Lambrinos L., Dosis A. (2013). *DisAssist: An internet of things and mobile communications platform for disabled parking space management*. Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM), 2810-2815.
2. Muñoz E., Serrano M, Marqués A., Handte M, Wagner S. (2015) *SIMON: asSisted MobIllity for Older aNd impaired users*. In Proceedings 22nd ITS World Congress, Boudeaux..
3. Muñoz E., Serrano M., Vivó M., Marqués A., Ferreras A., Solaz J. (2016) *SIMON: asSisted Mobility for Older aNd impaired users*. 6th Transport Research Arena, Warsaw, Poland. April 2016.
4. Corcho, O. *A linked data dataset for Madrid transport authority's datasets*. Slideshare. [Online] <http://es.slideshare.net/ocorcho/a-linked-data-dataset-for-madrid-transport-authoritys-datasets>.